

A NEW FIBER-BUNDLE BASED MODELING APPROACH FOR THE ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE PRESSURE VESSELS

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ABSTRACT

Filament-wound composite pressure vessels are usually modeled using a multi-layered approach based on the classical laminate theory. Given the realities of practical filament-wound structures, this approach may not be satisfactory in critical areas like the polar openings and turning zones, with respect to transition patterns or when faced with layers lacking full surface coverage. Effects of band stacking or effects due to the finite bandwidth may not be represented sufficiently by the layered approach, as the relevant model data (fiber angle and layer thickness) is not uniquely defined. A new approach motivated by the tenets of netting analysis and based on a finite element formulation with an embedded fiber-bundle model is being explored. This approach can be seen as an extension of modeling with reinforcing elements and is implemented as a generalization of a layered finite element formulation. The necessary model input data in the form of the fiber-bundle trajectories is generated using an advanced filament winding simulation. This work leads to improved understanding of the stress state in production filament-wound composite pressure vessels and thus enables more accurate design by analysis procedures. Furthermore, the improved modeling of discontinuous and non-layered fiber architectures may enable optimizations relying on the combined use of filament winding, overbraiding and fiber placement for the construction of composite pressure vessels.

1 INTRODUCTION

The interest in gas storage for mobile applications is steadily growing. This leads to a rising demand for lightweight composite pressure vessels. However, the behavior of composite structures is unintuitive and not easy to predict. The safe and efficient design of composite pressure vessels therefore requires thorough analysis [1].

Important features of composite materials and filament winding are described briefly to give the necessary background for the discussion of finite element analysis methods for composite pressure vessels (CPV) and to motivate the present work.

1.1 Fibrous Composite Materials

Structural composites are generally defined as materials consisting of two or more phases on a macroscopic scale, whose mechanical performance are designed to be superior to those of the constituent materials acting independently [2]. In particular, fiber-reinforced plastic materials consist of stiff and strong fibers embedded in a soft matrix material. Material in fiber form exhibits the highest tensile strength of all material forms. However, the strength of the fiber is reduced with increased length due to the higher probability of a local weakness. Embedding a multitude of parallel fibers at high volume fraction in a soft matrix material enables them to share loads and to mitigate the consequences of local failure, among other benefits.

It is important to note that this unidirectional fiber-reinforced composite material has excellent stiffness and strength properties only in fiber direction. In general it is necessary to combine multiple layers of unidirectional material with different fiber directions in a laminate to accommodate all loads acting on a structure. The resulting laminate properties usually still show a high directional dependency. Recognizing that the matrix dominated strength properties are much less certain and reproducible than the strength in fiber direction, it is clear that the design should generally not depend

on them strongly. Realizing the benefits of fiber-reinforced composite materials for structural application requires a considerably higher analysis effort than the use of traditional structural materials.

1.2 Filament Winding

Filament winding is one of the oldest manufacturing methods for structural composites [4]. Wet winding has the advantages of using the raw materials, fiber and resin, in its direct form without intermediate processing steps. The manufacturing speed measured in mass per time is among the highest in comparison to other methods. In sum, this contributes to relatively low manufacturing costs for filament wound composite materials compared to other methods [5] and explains its continued importance.

In the filament winding process multiple rovings or tows, each composed of thousands of fibers, are formed to a flat band and are impregnated with a matrix material, usually a resin. A typical fiber volume fraction V_f is 60 %. The band is continuously deposited on a rotating mandrel, eventually covering the entire surface. The resulting winding pattern consists of multiple cycles, in each cycle the band follows a specific path along the winding surface, Fig. 1. This path is characterized by a certain angle α of the band and thus the fibers relative to the meridian of the winding surface. Usually the cylindrical part of the vessel is covered in such a way that the resulting layer is composed of two bands with opposing fiber angles ($+\alpha/-\alpha$) at each location.

Notable characteristics of the filament wound structure are the distribution of the winding angle and the layer thickness along the winding surface. The details depend on the winding pattern. Usually winding angle and thickness are constant in the cylindrical part of the vessel (α_0, t_0).

Figure 1: Fiber path and unidirectional band on the winding surface [8].

1.3 Analysis of Composite Pressure Vessels

Different analysis methods are available and in use for composite pressure vessels [6]. All have to take into account the special features arising in the filament wound composite structure as described before. Netting analysis deserves special mention as the first analysis method for composite pressure vessels, introducing the important concept and design principle that the fiber network takes all the loads [5]. However, only finite element analysis has the potential to model all relevant effects. A review of finite element analysis methods for filament wound composite pressure vessels was given in [7].

Figure 2: Example for fiber angle and thickness distribution [15].

2 FILAMENT WINDING SIMULATION

The effects of the filament winding process on the resulting fiber architecture are not self-evident and require analysis by filament winding simulation.

2.1 Fiber Path

The wet fiber can be deposited on the surface only on – or close to – a geodesic path without slipping. On a surface of revolution with local radius r the geodesic path is given by Clairaut's theorem [4, 5]:

$$r \sin(\alpha) = \text{const.} \quad (1)$$

The fiber is tangent at the polar opening with radius r_p , i.e. $\alpha(r_p) = 90^\circ$. These layers are called helical layers. For geodesic winding the fiber angle at each radius can be evaluated by Eqn. (2). Figure 2 shows an example for this fiber angle distribution. Some deviation from this path is possible if the surface friction or material adhesion is exploited.

$$\alpha(r) = \arcsin(r_p/r) \quad (2)$$

Layers with a constant winding angle close to 90° are called hoop layers and can only be applied in the cylindrical part of the vessel. The polar opening radius of these layers is equal to or close to the radius in the cylindrical part of the vessel. Practical designs require multiple helical and hoop layers each with different winding angle α_0 and corresponding polar opening diameters.

2.2 Layer Thickness

One feature of the continuous filament winding process is that the same number of fibers crosses each parallel of the winding surface. This results in a constant layer thickness in the cylindrical part of the vessel. However, the layer thickness increases with decreasing vessel radius. This is a consequence of the progressive band overlap that can be easily recognized in Fig. 1 and Fig. 3. The resulting layer thickness distribution is shown in Fig. 2. This behavior can be approximately described by Eqn. (3) up to a certain distance from the polar opening.

$$t(r) = t_0 r_0 \cos(\alpha_0) / r \cos(\alpha) \quad (3)$$

Improved prediction of the layer thickness is possible by empirical or analytical methods [6] and by the enhanced filament winding simulation [8].

2.3 Enhanced Filament Winding Simulation

The main differences between the real fiber architecture of filament wound vessels and the idealized theory as described above can be recognized by explicit consideration of the finite fiber bandwidth w in an enhanced version of the filament winding simulation.

After computing the fiber path, the geometry of the fiber band, usually consisting of multiple parallel fiber strands, is modeled, Fig 1. Patches of triangles connecting consecutive bounding points represent the fiber band. The local thickness is computed by accumulation of band patches at sampling points on the winding surface. Likewise the local laminate stacking sequence at any sampling point can be computed. Details are presented in [8].

Figure 3: Overlap of the unidirectional band in the dome and near the polar opening [8].

2.4 Local Laminate Properties

The main results of the simulated band deposition on the winding surface are consistent with observations that can also be made with actual vessels manufactured by filament winding. The differences between the real laminate structure and the idealized theory are mainly due to the finite width w of the filament band. They are reduced with decreasing width of the band. Additional differences may exist due to fiber bridging effects.

The main observations are:

1. The effective thickness distribution along the meridian direction is not continuous as in Fig. 2, but stepped due to the band overlap.
2. The thickness at a given meridian position in circumferential direction is not constant but variable and depends on the winding pattern.
3. The local fiber angle within a layer at a given meridian and circumferential position is not constant in the circumferential direction (Fig. 3) and is in general not given by Clairaut's theorem as shown in Fig. 2.

In sum, the important local properties fiber angle and layer thickness possess a discontinuous distribution in the laminate. For optimized composite pressure vessel designs it is of high interest to examine the effects of these observations on the structural behavior.

2.5 Representation of Local Properties in the Analysis Model

The transfer of the laminate data generated by the enhanced filament winding simulation into the finite element model may proceed as follows: In the simplest case, the grid points representing the winding surface are used as nodal points of the finite element discretization. The finite elements may be shell or solid elements. However, only solid elements allow for the required detailed analysis. In the case of solid elements the grid points represent the nodes on the inner surface and the nodes on the outside surface are generated using the normal vectors of the winding surface and the thickness data. The required thickness information for each node is taken from the accumulated band thickness at the nodal points. Depending on the element type, the internal laminate description may allow for multiple layers with constant thickness and constant angle of principle material direction or for variable thickness layers with variable angle of principle material direction. In the latter case, the thickness and angle data usually have to be input at the nodal points. However, most finite element formulations require that the layers are continuous within the element and thus that the number of layers is the same at all nodes.

It turns out that this may not be the case for general filament wound structures. The easiest solution to this problem is to use a sampling point in the center of the element to record the local laminate stacking sequence and to use this data to define the laminate corresponding to the entire element. This may represent the real stiffness and strength distribution poorly. A more accurate approach may be to use the location of the in-plane integration points of the element as the sampling points, e.g. for 4 x 4 in-plane Gauss integration. Different laminate stacking sequences with individual number of layers would result at the in-plane integration points, making special element formulations necessary.

A mesh layout which respects the detailed description of the real laminate as shown e.g. in Fig. 3 within the framework of a laminate theory is hard to envision.

To avoid the mentioned problems, in the present research the filament wound band is modeled as a group of fiber bundles following the real fiber path on the winding surface. The fiber bundles are embedded in a structured mesh representing the matrix material.

3 FINITE ELEMENTS FOR FILAMENT WOUND STRUCTURES

The finite element analysis of composite laminates based on the assumptions of the classical laminate theory is described e.g. in [9]. The most appropriate representation, especially for thick-walled vessels, can be achieved using layered solid elements. In general multiple elements in thickness direction are necessary [7]. Shell elements are beyond the scope of this discussion.

3.1 Layered Solid Elements

The concept of the layered solid element is reviewed in two versions for constant and for variable layer thickness. Details of the mathematical formulation are discussed in [15].

One example for the formulation of the layered solid element for constant thickness layers is proposed in [10].

An element formulation allowing for variable element thickness – among other features – is proposed in [12].

3.2 Reinforcing Element

The application of truss elements embedded in solid elements for the modeling of dry filament wound pressure vessels was proposed in [13]. This can be realized by constraining the nodal degrees of freedom of the truss element to the degrees of freedom of the embedding solid element. Thus the displacement field of the solid element imposes the displacements of all embedded truss elements.

The same effect can be achieved by classical reinforcing elements as described e.g. in [14].

Using this transformation the stiffness matrix of the reinforcing element can be expressed in terms of the degrees of freedom of the embedding element and superimposed to form the total stiffness. Typically, the reinforcing element allows the definition of multiple reinforcing members. This formulation is restricted to unidirectional reinforcement in the direction of the reinforcing members.

This may be appropriate for the modeling of dry filament wound structures without use of matrix materials or for analysis on the basis of the assumption of netting analysis.

For the modeling of a filament wound structure the global fiber architecture must be mapped on the reinforcing members in the individual elements.

Figure 4: Reinforcing element embedded in a solid element. Fiber bundle element [15].

3.3 Fiber Bundle Element

The idea of the fiber bundle element is to form a synthesis of the layered element and the reinforcing element as a practical meso-level model for the fiber architectures arising from filament winding.

In a first variant a prismatic shape that can be mapped on a cube models the geometry of each fiber bundle. This variant is similar to the layered element with variable layer thickness as described in [12, 15] but has a generalized geometry of the second isoparametric map, Fig. 4. The parameters ξ_i now contain *the coordinates of the fiber bundle* under consideration. This variant of the fiber bundle element may use the same Gauss integration formula as the layered element.

In a second variant a volume simply computed from length and cross section area models each fiber bundle. This variant is similar to the reinforcing element described before but allows the alternative use of a one-dimensional or a three-dimensional constitutive model. In the latter case the reinforcement is not purely unidirectional. This variant could use a one-point integration rule.

$$\mathbf{K}_{eIJ} = \sum_{B=1}^{nbundle} \sum_{ip=1}^{nip} \mathbf{B}_I^T(\xi_{ip}^B) \mathbf{C}_B \mathbf{B}_J(\xi_{ip}^B) \det \mathbf{J}(\xi_{ip}^B) \det \mathbf{J}^B(\mathbf{r}_{ip}^B) w_{ip}^B \quad (4)$$

The differences between the two variants are the number of integration points, the effective formulas for the Jacobian matrix of the second isoparametric map \mathbf{J}^B and the weighting factor w_{ip}^B of the integration points in the evaluation of the element stiffness matrix, Eqn. (4). Both variants employ the constitutive matrix \mathbf{C} for the fiber bundle B for a one- or three-dimensional constitutive model.

The first variant may be more costly than the second variant due to the higher number of integration points. However, evaluation of the relative efficiency is subject to verification of the element behavior.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The enhanced filament winding simulation confirms the observation that filament wound composite pressure vessel structures possess discontinuous fiber angle and layer thickness distributions. This poses difficulties for the accurate modeling using layered elements based on the assumptions of the classical laminate theory. Consideration of the implementation of layered solid elements and reinforcing elements motivates the formulation of a fiber bundle element that may be more effective for the analysis of filament wound structures. Implementation of this concept is proceeding and requires further work in the infrastructure of the enhanced filament winding simulation and in testing of the fiber bundle element. The fiber bundle approach may be the appropriate bridge between micro and macro descriptions of the composite materials resulting from filament winding and may be extended to structures arising from fiber placement and braiding processes. The results are relevant for the safe and economic design of optimized high-pressure hydrogen tanks for automotive applications.

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